

VALIDATION OF UNSTEADY SURFACE PRESSURE PREDICTIONS FOR MT1 RIG TURBINE BLADES

Dr. Davendu Y. Kulkarni[†]
Aeromechanical Engineer
Rolls-Royce plc.,
Derby, UK

Prof. Kam Chana[§]
Oxford Thermofluids Institute
Department of Engineering Science,
University of Oxford, UK

ABSTRACT

Modern turbomachinery components, sub-systems and engine architectures are nowadays designed and assessed using high-fidelity Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) based methods. Many key design, testing and in-service operation decisions are also taken based on the CFD results. Therefore, the computational tool that generates these results must be reliable and validated to ensure its prediction accuracy.

This paper presents the validation study conducted for Rolls-Royce inhouse CFD code – Hydra against the measured data obtained from the MT1 high pressure (HP) turbine test rig at Oxford Turbine Test Facility (OTRF). The MT1 turbine rig experimental set-up and relevant instrumentation are described, and the test data processing methodology is explained. Further details of the MT1 HP turbine stage domains, meshes, analysis set-ups and Hydra prediction methodology are given. It is demonstrated that the flow parameters obtained from Hydra steady CFD match to that of MT1 test rig within the measurement tolerance of $\pm 2\%$.

The predicted unsteady blade surface pressure amplitudes are compared to that obtained from experimental tests at multiple unsteady pressure probe locations on the rotor blade surface. The uncertainty quantification studies show that the mean pressure magnitudes are overpredicted by +7%, whereas unsteady pressure amplitudes can vary by $\pm 10\%$ on an average compared to the measured test data. These results demonstrate that Hydra produces test-equivalent surface pressure variation, which is advantageous for estimating the sub-system performance, for modelling the unsteady aerodynamics in multi-stage turbomachines and for assessing the effects of unsteady flows on various aeroelastic phenomena.

Keywords: MT1 turbine test rig, OTRF, Hydra CFD tool, Unsteady Aerodynamics, Experimental Validation, Aeroelasticity

ABBREVIATIONS

BL	Boundary Layer
CFD	Computational Fluid Dynamics
FA	Full Annulus
FMG	Full Multi-Grid
HCF	High Cycle Fatigue
HP / IP / LP	High / Intermediate / Low Pressure
MT1	Military Turbine 1
NGV	Nozzle Guide Vane
PL	Phase-Lag
SA	Spalart-Allmaras turbulence model
SFC	Specific Fuel Consumption
SPMR	Single Passage Multi-Row
TATEF-II	Turbine Aerothermal External Flows – II

NOMENCLATURE

C	Turbine capacity [$kg\sqrt{K}/Pa.s$]
γ	Ratio of specific heats [-]
k	Turbulence kinetic energy [J/kg]
\dot{m}	Mass flow rate [kg/s]
N	Number of NGV passing events
N_{sect}	Number of sectors [-]
N_{steps}	Number of time steps selected [-]
ω	rotational speed [rpm], Turbulence dissipation rate [m^2/s^3]
P_t	Total pressure [Pa]
P_s	Static pressure [Pa]
$P(n, \tau)$	Instantaneous pressure signal [Pa]
\bar{P}	Ensembled averaged pressure signal [Pa]
\mathfrak{R}	Turbine blade reaction [-]
τ	Real time step, NGV passing time [s]
y^+	Non-dimensional wall distance [-]

[†] Corresponding author

[§] Commercial and Technical Director of Oxford Turbine Research Facility

1. INTRODUCTION

The ever-increasing demand for reducing the specific fuel consumption, emissions, and noise and for improving the reliability and mechanical integrity of aero gas turbines has led to the development of modern ultra-high bypass ratio geared turbofan architectures. In these new engine architectures, both HP and LP turbine rotors will operate at higher pressure ratios and rotational speeds compared to that in the conventional engines to achieve optimum efficiency. As a result, the turbine rotor blades, especially the HP turbine blades, might be subjected to higher steady and vibratory loading. This necessitates performing thorough aeroelastic assessments to ensure their mechanical integrity in various engine operating conditions.

It is well-known that at resonance condition the upstream vane count engine order excitations generate high vibratory loading on the turbine rotor blades. This vibratory loading excites the crossing blade vibration modes in the operational speed range. Despite the presence of aerodynamic and mechanical friction damping, the resonant response of blades leads to the generation of high vibratory stresses at the blade-root and in the shank. The combined steady and vibratory stresses increase the high-cycle fatigue (HCF) endurance or the stress ratio in the blade. It is important that the HCF endurance should not exceed a pre-determined criterion ensuring the mechanical integrity of turbine rotor blades. HCF endurance prediction heavily depends on the accurate estimation of various aeromechanical and structural parameters, such as modal force, damping, peak response, mode frequency, mode-shape etc. for each vibration mode of interest [1]. These parameters in turn depend on the correct prediction of the magnitude and phase of unsteady static pressure on turbine blade surfaces. Clearly, the understanding of unsteady surface pressure variation plays a key role in determining the aeromechanical behavior of a turbine blade. It is, therefore, important that the computational tool used for unsteady pressure predictions is reliable and validated against the test data. Therefore, the first objective of the present study is to validate the unsteady pressures predicted using Hydra against that obtained from MT1 HP turbine test rig.

Currently, it is a common practice to employ single-passage multi-row phase-lag methods to perform fast unsteady aerodynamic analyses instead of using the full annulus multi-row methods due to their prohibitively high computational time-cost. Single-passage methods are quite useful to quickly assess a given blade design, and to perform the fast design sensitivity and robustness studies; thus, allowing the development of optimized blade designs within the given timescales. Clearly, the single-passage methods must be sufficiently representative of the full-annulus methods. Therefore, the second objective of this work is to cross-validate the results of single-passage phase lag method against that of full-annulus method and the MT1 rig test data to develop good confidence.

The third objective of this work is to quantify the variability of unsteady pressure predictions generated by the computational tool. The variation in unsteady pressure predictions are known to be generated due to the variations of geometry fidelity, mesh parameters, analyses setups and also due to the turbulence

models. These variations infiltrate into various aeromechanical parameters and reflect through the variation of predicted HCF endurance. The present study shows the effect of turbulence model variation on the unsteady surface pressure predictions. This uncertainty quantification is important to understand the mismatch between CFD and test data and to develop an evaluative judgement.

2. EXPERIMENTAL SET-UP

2.1 Background

The current validation and unsteady quantification studies are performed using the measured test data acquired from MT1 turbine test rig. The MT1 rig was designed by Rolls-Royce in the mid-1980s and was first tested in an aerodynamic rig at Bristol. This full-sized aero engine rotating HP turbine stage was first installed in the Isentropic Light Piston Facility (ILPF) at RAE Pyestock in early 1990s [2, 3, 4]. It was relocated to DERA Farnborough in 2004. Since operational, the MT1 rig facility has generated experimental data for many test campaigns, such as IACA (Investigation of the Aerodynamics and Cooling of Advanced Engine Turbine Components) and TATEF (Turbine Aerothermal External Flows) etc. It was primarily developed to investigate aerothermal aspects of the HP turbine and is well-known for producing high quality aerodynamic and heat transfer data at a relatively low cost and with excellent scaling of non-dimensional parameters [5]. In 2010, the MT1 rig was moved to the Oxford Thermofluids Institute, Oxford University and renamed as the Oxford Turbine Research Facility (OTRF) [5].

The experimental data used for the current work was generated during TATEF-II research programme [6] started in 2004. The TATEF-II was part of EU's 6th Framework Programme, which was aimed at building an experimental database to evaluate the unsteady effects of aggressive inlet flow conditions such as, inlet swirls, enhanced hot spots and of the film cooling and rotor platform cooling in HPTs with strong shock waves on the turbine blade cooling and stage efficiency. This database also helped to develop the physical understanding of complex flow phenomena such as unsteady heat transfer and aerodynamic losses in the presence of turbine external flows. Major achievements of TATEF-II programme are claimed to be the accurate measurement of multi-row turbine efficiency [7, 8] taking into account the inlet flow distortions, shock structures in bladerows and blade cooling in transonic flows with cooling holes entrance effects. TATEF-II results have been extensively used by the industrial partners to validate their design tools and to assess mainly the aerothermal performance and heat transfer.

The MT1 test rig is instrumented to measure the unsteady static pressures on the rotor blade surfaces. This data was used previously to understand the link between surface pressures and heat transfer phenomena [9, 10]. This paper presents the foremost usage of this database to understand the turbine blade aeromechanics; particularly the upstream vane count high engine order excitations on the rotor blade. Therefore, the main objective here is to validate the unsteady surface static pressures predicted using Rolls-Royce Hydra tool against the test data.

2.2 Rig Description

Figure 1 shows the general layout of MT1 test facility. It consists of a high-pressure reservoir, a pump-tube containing a light-weight piston, a fast-acting plug valve, the HP turbine stage (working section) and the turbo-brake. The operation of the test rig is described in [5, 11, 12]. When the high-pressure air from the reservoir is injected into the piston tube behind the light piston, the free piston moves down the piston tube thereby compressing and heating the air in front of it isentropically. When the required working pressure and temperature are achieved the fast-acting plug valve is opened. The air flows out of the piston tube into the large annulus, where it settles and enters the working section through a contraction at the inlet of the turbine stage. The test run ends when the piston reaches the end of the piston tube. Steady flow conditions are achieved for approximately 0.5s, during which the experimental data are acquired. The short-duration operation of this rig allows the transient heat transfer evaluation from the temperature-time history at a fraction of the cost of continuous flow facilities.

FIGURE 1: SCHEMATIC OF MT-1 TURBINE TEST RIG [13, 11]

Figure 2 shows the working section of the MT1 test rig. The compressed, uniform, cold inflow enters the HP NGV, where it is throttled and swirled to drive the HP rotor blades. The flow expands in the HP rotor bladerow and imparts kinetic energy into the blades based on the reaction principle to produce mechanical work. Downstream of the rotor the flow passes through a sudden expansion chamber and then it is throttled in the second throat. The second throat is a fully annular, variable area device, which is choked to isolate the HP test blade operation from downstream flow disturbances. It controls the rig mass flow rate, sets the blade exit static pressure and hence the stage pressure ratio and also maintains the exit flow symmetry. The HP shaft is supported on two sets of deep-groove, annular contact ball bearings, which are lubricated through a dedicated oil flow system [11].

On the other end of the HP shaft, the aerodynamic axial turbobrake [14] is mounted along with its bypass and blockage rings assembly. The turbobrake is designed to absorb the mechanical energy produced by the turbine and is tuned to hold the turbine rotational speed constant within $\pm 0.5\%$ of the design speed throughout the experiment [11, 12]. It allows safe and consistent operation of the rig without requiring more complex energy absorbing devices such as, mechanical brakes or a flywheel.

FIGURE 2: THE TEST SECTION OF MT1 RIG [6, 15]

The MT1 rig consists of the unshrouded high-pressure research turbine blades that are relevant to the civil turbine subsystem designs. The HP stage has 32 NGVs and 60 rotor blades. The NGV bladerow is designed to have 20 fixed NGVs and 12 fully instrumented NGVs arranged into 3 removable cassettes with 4 vanes per cassette. The NGVs and rotor blades are manufactured from Aluminum. Rotor blades instrumented with heat transfer and surface pressure transducers are cast in Inco and coated with enamel. This allows electrical connections to be painted on the surface of the enamel. Each removable NGV cassette provides the access to four rotor blades; thus, making it easy to access, to fit and to test the instrumented blades and vanes without disassembling the whole rig. NGVs have hub and tip fillet of 2.5mm, whereas rotor blades have hub fillet of 0.55mm as displayed in Fig. 3. Both NGVs and rotor blades have been separately tested, and their test results are heavily documented and published earlier [16, 17, 18, 19]. The test rig is tuned to run at constant design speed of 9500rpm and rotor blade tip gap at design condition is estimated to be 0.56mm. Table 1 shows the turbine design point parameters relevant to the current work along with their ranges and some important non-dimensional variables.

FIGURE 3: MT1 TURBINE BLADE GEOMETRY

TABLE 1: MT1 RIG DESIGN AND OPERATIONAL PARAMETERS AND THEIR RANGES [5, 11]

Parameter [unit]	Measurement location (Refer to Fig. 4)	Measured and radially averaged, \pm variation	Operation range
NGV inlet total pressure [bar]	Plane D	4.6 \pm 2%	0 - 10
NGV inlet total temperature [K]	Plane D	444.4 \pm 2%	293 - 530
NGV exit isentropic Mach number [-]	Plane I	0.98 \pm 2%	-
NGV exit static pressure [bar]	Plane I	2.475 \pm 2%	-
Rotor relative inlet total pressure [bar]	Plane I	2.707 \pm 2%	-
Rotor exit static pressure [bar]	Plane F	1.431 \pm 2%	-
Rotational speed [rpm]	-	9500 \pm 2%	4000 - 10000
Rig mass flow rate [kg/s]	-	17.4	-
HP stage total to static pressure ratio [-]	-	3.2	-
Reynolds number [-]	Plane I	2.6E+06	-
Specific speed [rpm/\sqrt{K}]	-	439.2	-
Stage inlet capacity [$kg \sqrt{K}/s.KPa$]	Plane D	12.1	-
Rotor reaction [-]	Rotor LE - TE	0.45	-
Run time [ms]	-	400	300 - 1700
Rotor blade mid-span radius [m]	-	0.2746	-
Rotor blade axial chord at mid-span [m]	-	0.0275	-

FIGURE 4: A SCHEMATIC VIEW OF MT1 HP TURBINE RIG GENERAL ASSEMBLY, MEASUREMENT PLANES AND THE LOCATIONS OF SURFACE MOUNTED KULITE PRESSURE TRANSDUCERS

2.3 Instrumentation and Data Acquisition

The MT1 rig has a wide range of data measurement instruments and data acquisition systems, which are aimed at recording detailed aerodynamic and heat transfer data. This paper, however, describes the instrumentation that is relevant to the present work. Other instrumentation details can be found in [11, 12, 8, 5, 7, 20]. The span-wise and circumferential variation of total pressure and total temperature of incoming flow is measured using traversing probes located far upstream of the NGVs (plane ‘D’). The rig mass flow rate is measured at the piston tube exit location as described in [21].

As shown in Fig. 4, flush mounted time-averaged (steady) static pressure tappings are located at the upstream of NGVs (plane ‘D’), downstream of the NGVs (plane ‘I’) and at the downstream of the rotor blade (plane ‘F’) on both hub and casing surfaces at 120° circumferential spacing [22]. These pressure transducer signals are measured using a fast-acting Scanivalve Hyscan system and are sampled at 555Hz [11, 12]. This data is recorded on a low-speed data acquisition system.

The unsteady static pressures on MT1 HP rotor blade surfaces are measured using miniature semiconductor pressure transducers (Kulites), which are designed to measure high frequency pressure fluctuations. These transducers are mounted flush to the blade surface [4], which is a technique pioneered at Oxford University [10]. A total of seventeen Kulites are located on the suction and pressure surfaces of four cast Inco blades as shown in Fig. 4. Moreover, an additional Kulite is housed in the Kiel probe located at the leading edge of 4 Aluminum rotor blades to measure the blade inlet relative total pressure. All these transducers are mounted on a mid-height streamline as shown in Fig. 4 and Fig. 5. Figure 4 also shows the Kulite indexing [22].

FIGURE 5: ROTOR BLADE INSTRUMENTATION FOR UNSTEADY SURFACE PRESSURE MEASUREMENTS

The time resolved measurements obtained from unsteady pressure transducers are recorded on a Prosig AD3000 high performance data acquisition system [12, 22], which is capable of sampling at the maximum rate of 1MHz. At this sampling rate this data acquisition system records 6000 data points per rotor revolution. In the 400ms useful run-time of MT1 rig, the system acquires measured data points worth 60 rotor revolutions simultaneously for 20 data channels.

2.4 Experimental Data Processing

During the rig tests, various kinds of experimental data was collected across multiple measurement stations of the MT1 rig such as unsteady heat transfer and surface pressures, time-averaged total pressure, static pressure allowing the evaluation of Mach numbers throughout the stage. During the data processing [22, 23], a short segment of data from the middle of the run history is extracted. All unsteady data was passed through 200kHz low-pass filter. The unsteady pressure data taken from different runs conducted on different days and with different ambient conditions is initially phase-locked or phase-referenced such that the zero-time for each signal corresponds to exactly the same NGV-rotor alignment as shown in Fig. 6. The signal quality of this data is excellent, which clearly shows the particular pressure wake signature of each NGV, probably caused by small profile differences arising from manufacturing processes.

FIGURE 6: EXPERIMENTAL UNSTEADY PRESSURE DATA PROCESSING [22, 23]

Further, the mean pressure is removed from the raw pressure signal and the pressure fluctuations are ensemble averaged using the eq. (1) [23] from all transducers.

$$\bar{P}(\tau) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N P(n, \tau) \quad (1)$$

Ensemble averaging of the static pressure signal on a NGV pitch-to-pitch basis produced the single NGV passing event, representing a typical NGV pressure signal. Figure 6 shows the excellent agreement between the ensembled averaged data and the raw pressure signal for 5 NGV passing events. This averaged signal is scaled by the ratio of average rotor relative total pressures to remove any run-to-run variations. The mean pressure is then added back to the averaged signal; making it ready to compare to the idealized NGV-rotor unsteady pressure fluctuations predicted by time-accurate CFD codes.

Over the years, MT1 rig has undergone multiple modifications in terms of layout, supporting systems, component designs and instrumentation [5, 24]. For the present work, the data collected during the phase-I of the TATEF programme is used, in which both NGVs and blades of MT1 rig were uncooled. During phase-II, the NGVs were film-cooled, and in phase-III, film cooling was introduced for both NGVs and blades. Further, inlet temperature distortion devices were installed to study the effect of hot spots. After this, the rig was extended to 1.5 stages by introducing IP NGVs to investigate the interaction of IP vanes with the HP turbine stage [13, 8]. Shrouded blade designs and casing-shroud cooling investigations were conducted by updating the turbine rotor blade design [25, 26]. The rig instrumentation was upgraded to accurately measure the turbine shaft torque, power and absolute efficiency to within $\pm 2\%$ [7]. The inlet temperature non-uniformity and its effects on turbine efficiency were studied by developing advanced inlet swirl and the hot-streak simulation devices [27, 15, 20]. Currently, the facility is being upgraded for a long-duration test rig, the details of which can be found elsewhere [24].

3. PREDICTION METHODOLOGY

3.1 Flow Domain and Geometry

The high-fidelity unsteady CFD models of MT1 HP turbine stage are developed to predict the unsteady surface pressures on rotor blade surfaces. Figure 7 shows the MT1 rig geometry used for the present numerical investigations. The HP stage domain extends from measurement plane ‘D’ to plane ‘F’ (see Fig. 4). The NGV and rotor blade domains are coupled through a pair of sliding interface planes, located downstream of the measurement plane ‘I’. This geometry is used to produce single-passage and full-annulus models shown in Fig. 8.

FIGURE 7: MT1 HP TURBINE GEOMETRY AND FLOW BOUNDARY CONDITIONS

The MT1 CFD model comprises high-fidelity geometries of both HP NGV and HP blade. NGVs have 2.5mm hub and tip fillet radii, whereas blades have 0.55mm hub fillet radius. These geometry features aid the simulation of flow blockages and flow features at the hub and tip of MT1 blades. The rotor blade has a constant tip gap of 0.56mm, which is same as the actual tip gap reported during MT1 tests. The rotor blade platform length is modelled as per the actual blade geometry. The hub and casing surfaces of NGVs and blade also incorporate cooling flow slots; however, those are not modelled as flow inlets or exits.

FIGURE 8: MT1 HP TURBINE FLOW DOMAINS

3.2 Mesh Generation

The flow domains of the HP NGV and rotor blade are meshed using Rolls-Royce in-house proprietary mesh generator - PADRAM. This tool generates rapid, fully automated, body-conformal, high-quality, multi-block, structured grids for various turbomachinery components [28, 29]. PADRAM also allows parameterization and meshing of various complex geometry features to generate the high-fidelity CFD models [30]. It is capable of generating template-topology based structured grids as well as fully flexible unstructured meshes in the same domain.

FIGURE 9: MT1 NGV AND BLADE MESHES AT MID-SPAN

Figure 9 shows the top view of blade-centric structured grids of HP NGV and HP rotor blade at mid-span. These grids are selected after performing grid convergence study based on 5 mesh coarseness levels. It is ensured that the selected grid maintains a good mesh density at flow mixing regions, correctly captures the blade shock structure and miniature flow features at the blade tip gap, predicts the correct capacity-reaction and blade loading and is also suitable for the $k-\omega$ turbulence model used for this work. The mesh nodes are distributed around the blade profiles to accurately represent the blade leading and trailing edge shapes. Both NGV and blade grids consist of 12 layers of O-grid or the boundary layer grid. The thickness of the first layer of O-grid is selected such that near wall y^+ is close to 1. The blade tip gap is discretized using 20 layers of structured grid. As shown in the inset of Fig. 9, both NGV and blade grids consist of wake mesh at the trailing edge to capture the shape, size and direction of flow wakes. The same number of radial layers (see the side view in Fig. 10) and a similar tangential node spacing is employed to match the NGV and blade grids at the interface plane. The NGV grid consists of approx. 2.2M nodes, whereas rotor blade consists of 2.91M nodes; totaling approx. 5.1M nodes in the single passage multi-row stage model. This single-passage grid is then expanded in circumferential direction to generate the full annulus mesh, which contains approx. 240M nodes.

FIGURE 10: SIDE VIEW OF MT1 NGV AND BLADE MESHES

3.3 Boundary Conditions

For all numerical investigations, non-reflecting subsonic inlet boundary conditions are specified at the NGV inlet plane in the form of radial distribution of inlet total pressure and total temperature. The exit boundary conditions are applied in the form of exit static pressure at the rotor exit plane.

All solid walls are specified as impermeable, adiabatic, viscous wall boundaries with slip condition. Rotational speed boundary conditions are applied to the HP rotor blade and HP blade platform. Table 1 shows the flow and rotational speed boundary conditions for MT1 rig operation point.

For the $k-\omega$ turbulence model, the inlet turbulence intensity is specified as 6% as per the rig measurements, whereas turbulence length scale is calculated as 15% of the rotor inlet span, which is approx. 0.009. For the SA turbulence model, the inlet turbulence intensity is used as 0.01. A real gas model is employed in combination with $k-\omega$ turbulence model, whereas a perfect gas model is used with SA turbulence model.

3.4 Analysis Set-up

The present numerical investigations are conducted using Rolls-Royce in-house aero-thermal CFD solver – Hydra [31, 32, 33]. Hydra is an unstructured, vertex-centered, edge-based, finite-volume solver of the compressible Reynolds Averaged Navier-Stokes (RANS) equations. It incorporates a suite of non-linear, linear and adjoint solvers [34, 35] that can operate on hybrid structured and unstructured meshes. The spatial discretization is performed using the second order edge based approximate Riemann solver of Roe [36]. The flow equations are integrated around median-dual control volumes using a MUSCL based flux-differencing algorithm. The discrete flow equations are preconditioned using a block Jacobi preconditioner and time marched using the multi-stage Runge-Kutta scheme. Convergence is accelerated using an element-collapsing multigrid algorithm. The parallelization of the code is carried out using MPI through the interfacing OPLUS library [37]. This flow solver can run in parallel on both shared and distributed memory machines using domain decomposition.

For the present work, the multi-block PADRAM meshes are converted into the Hydra data structure using a pre-processor. The pre-processor generates full-annulus blade-rows and applies both flow and rotational boundary conditions. The fluid is modelled as both the real gas and perfect gas. The unsteady computations are performed using 2nd order spatial discretization and 2nd order dual time stepping method [38]. The real time step (τ) calculations for full-annulus computations are illustrated in eq. (2). The time step depends on the sector size and number of steps per period, both of which are calculated considering that the integer number of NGVs and blades are incorporated into the domain. For full-annulus computations, the number of sectors (N_{sect}) is 1, whereas for phase-lag computations, it is considered as 4. A proportional number of time-steps (N_{steps}) is selected for FA and PL computations equivalent to one revolution of the rotor.

$$\tau = \frac{t_{period} / 360^{\circ} \text{ sector}}{N_{steps}} = \frac{2 \pi}{\omega N_{sect} N_{steps}} \quad (2)$$

$$\tau = \frac{2 \pi}{994.8 * 1 * 1920} = 3.2895e^{-6} \text{ s}$$

Fluid viscosity effects are modelled using both $k-\omega$ and Spalart-Allmaras (SA) turbulence models with wall function. The single passage phase-lag unsteady computations are performed using 40 cores, whereas the full-annulus computations are performed using 400 cores. The convergence was accelerated using 4 V-cycle multi-grid levels. The computations are considered to be converged when blade surface pressure achieves periodic variation. Numerical probes were incorporated into all unsteady computations at the NGV exit and on the rotor blade surfaces as shown in Fig. 11. The locations of these numerical probes are exactly matched to the Kulites and other steady pressure tapings used during MT1 rig tests. The single passage phase-lag cases required approx. 1 week, whereas the full-annulus cases required approx. 10 weeks to generate the converged time-history of unsteady pressures.

FIGURE 11: LOCATIONS OF NUMERICAL PROBES IN HYDRA COMPUTATIONS

4. RESULTS

Initially, steady-state single-passage Hydra computations were performed to initialize the flow solution, to check the mesh parameter sensitivity and y^+ values and to observe the NGV and blade loading, static temperature distribution and the NGV wake shape and direction etc. The steady-state solutions were then used to initiate the full-annulus (FA) and phase-lag (PL) unsteady computations.

Figure 12 shows the comparison of MT1 turbine stage capacity (\mathcal{C}) and blade reaction (\mathfrak{R}) against that measured during the MT1 test rig tests. The capacity and reaction are calculated as shown in eq. (3) and eq. (4).

$$\mathcal{C} = \left\{ \frac{\dot{m} \sqrt{T_t}}{P_t} \right\}_{NGV \text{ inlet}} \quad (3)$$

$$\mathfrak{R} = \frac{(T_s)_{Rotor \text{ inlet}} - (T_s)_{Rotor \text{ exit}}}{(T_t)_{NGV \text{ inlet}} - (T_t)_{Rotor \text{ exit}}} \quad (4)$$

FIGURE 12: COMPARISON OF STAGE CAPACITY AND BLADE REACTION WITH MT1 RIG TEST DATA

It can be observed that both the capacity and reaction predicted from Hydra unsteady computations are very close to the variation limits of test data; demonstrating that the test-equivalent boundary conditions have been applied to Hydra

unsteady simulations. The predicted results are, therefore, directly comparable to the test data.

Figure 13(a) to Figure 13(e) show comparison of various mean flow parameters predicted from unsteady simulations with those measured from rig tests. It can be seen that all the mean flow parameters, such as inlet total pressure and temperature, NGV exit static pressure and NGV exit isentropic Mach number and the rotor exit static pressure are well within the $\pm 2\%$ rig measurement variation limits. This indicates that the rig operation points simulated using all Hydra cases match to the measured rig operating condition.

Figure 13(f) shows the comparison of static pressure variation predicted from Hydra with the mean static pressure measured during the MT1 rig test. Note that the predicted rotor blade surface static pressures are extracted from Hydra unsteady simulations at the mid-span and are time-averaged for the comparison. Figure 13(f) demonstrates that all Hydra simulation cases generate a correct estimate of blade loading at the rig operation point.

Figure 14 and Figure 15 show the comparison of unsteady static pressure variation on the pressure and suction surfaces of MT1 rotor blade at mid span, respectively. They display the unsteady pressure variation generated due to the upstream vane passing event at the Kulites mounted on pressure and suction surfaces. The predicted pressure signals shown in both Fig. 14 and Fig. 15 are phase-referenced to the test data, and thus they can only provide intra-probe phase information. Fig. 14 and Fig. 15 show that both full-annulus and phase-lag models can capture all the important flow features at rotor mid-span location. Moreover, the intra-probe phase variation of unsteady pressures predicted from Hydra also qualitatively match well with the test data. Figure 15 also shows that the phase-lag method may not capture some of the unsteady flow features near the trailing edge of suction surface as shown by the pressure probes 1214, 1219 and 1215. The probe 1200 measures inlet relative total pressure, and it does not match well with the predictions potentially due to the misalignment of the probe with the flow direction.

For the present study, the quantification of unsteady pressure amplitude is particularly important to understand the prediction uncertainties. Therefore, the unsteady pressure signals shown in Fig. 14 and Fig. 15 are processed to find the mean pressure magnitude and the unsteady pressure amplitude. The mean pressure is calculated by taking the average of the max and min amplitudes of pressure signal, whereas the unsteady pressure amplitude is obtained as the difference between the maximum and minimum of the pressure signal. Further, both measured and predicted unsteady pressure time signals are processed through Fast Fourier Transformation (FFT) analyzer to obtain the spectral power in each harmonic of excitation frequency. Figure 16(a-f) show the Fourier transforms of unsteady pressures at six Kulite probes at the leading edge, mid-chord and near trailing edge positions on both suction and pressure surfaces of the rotor blade. The FFT results show that both full-annulus and single passage PL methods can capture the upstream NGV wake flow features and can accurately predict the unsteady pressure strength for each harmonic of NGV excitation frequency.

(a) Comparison of NGV inlet total pressure

(b) Comparison of NGV inlet total temperature

(c) Comparison of NGV exit static pressure

(d) Comparison of NGV exit Mach number

(e) Comparison of rotor exit static pressure

(f) Comparison of rotor blade loading at mid-span

FIGURE 13: COMPARISON OF MEAN FLOW PARAMETERS WITH MT1 RIG TEST DATA

FIGURE 14: COMPARISON OF UNSTEADY PRESSURE VARIATION ON MT1 BLADE PRESSURE SURFACE AT MID-SPAN

FIGURE 15: COMPARISON OF UNSTEADY PRESSURE VARIATION ON MT1 BLADE SUCTION SURFACE AT MID-SPAN

(a) Leading edge probe 1211

(b) Suction side leading edge curvature probe 1212

(c) Pressure side mid-chord probe 1203

(d) Suction side mid-chord probe 1218

(e) Pressure side trailing edge probe 1205

(f) Suction side trailing edge probe 1215

FIGURE 16: COMPARISON OF UNSTEADY PRESSURE SPECTRAL POWER AT SIX PROBE LOCATIONS AT MID-SPAN

It is observed from Fig. 16(e) and Fig. 16(f) that the variation of predicted unsteady pressure spectral power increases downstream of the mid-chord and near the blade trailing edge.

Figure 17 provides the summary of uncertainty quantification for the measured and predicted unsteady pressure predictions. It shows the unsteady pressure amplitudes plotted as a band about the mean pressure levels, obtained from Fig. 14 and Fig. 15. It is observed that Hydra overpredicts the mean pressure

by +7% on an average compared to the measured mean pressure, although it varies up to +20% at the mid-chord on suction surface. The unsteady pressure amplitude is observed to be overpredicted by $\pm 10\%$ on an average; however, it can vary by up to $\pm 25\%$ compared to the measured unsteady pressure magnitudes near the leading edge of pressure surface and near the trailing edge of suction surface due to the presence of passage shock.

FIGURE 17: UNCERTAINTY QUANTIFICATION OF THE STATIC PRESSURE ON ROTOR BLADE SURFACE

5. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

Validation studies of the Rolls-Royce inhouse CFD code - Hydra are presented here. Four different computational set-ups are developed to understand the effects of domain size, turbulence models and gas models on the unsteady pressure variation. The predicted mean and unsteady static pressures on rotor blade surfaces are compared to the test data obtained from the MT1 HP turbine test rig at OTRF.

It is concluded that the Hydra full-annulus unsteady analysis set-ups with $k-\omega$ and SA turbulence models produce similar results compared to the test data. Moreover, the phase-lag models produce very similar results compared to the full-annulus models. Note here that the phase-lag models are not able to capture some of the flow features near the trailing edge suction surface of the HP turbine blade, which might limit their application in certain conditions. The present study also shows that the real and perfect gas models do not seem to affect the unsteady pressure variations on blade surfaces; however, note that the fluid temperature effects could not be evaluated here owing to the cold inflow conditions. The uncertainty quantification studies show that the mean pressure magnitudes are overpredicted by +7%, whereas unsteady pressure amplitudes can vary by up to $\pm 10\%$ compared to the measured test data; which is a good qualitative match to the test data.

The present study and its conclusions are based on unsteady pressure amplitudes predicted for an uncooled stage with cold inflow conditions at 50%span. Future studies are recommended to understand the effects of hot non-uniform inlet flows, distorted inlet flows as well as the cooling flows on the unsteady pressure variations particularly near the rotor endwall regions. Moreover, it is deemed necessary to understand the interconnection between the unsteady pressure variations on blade surfaces and the magnitude of blade aerofoil and blade shank stresses.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Kulkarni D. Y. and Peng C., "On the Probabilistic Endurance Prediction Approach for Turbomachinery Blades and Vanes," in *ASME Turbo Expo, GT2020-14013*, pp. 1-13, 2020.
- [2] Jones T. V., Schultz D. L. and Hendley A. D., "On the Flow in an Isentropic Light Piston Tunnel," UK MoD, Aeronautical Research Council R&M No. 3731, 1973.
- [3] Brooks A. J., Colbourne D. E., Wedlake T. E., Jones T. V., Oldfield M. L. G., Schultz D. L. and Loftus P. J., "The Isentropic Light Piston Cascade at RAE Pyestock," AGARD-CP-390, 1985.
- [4] Ainsworth R. W., Schultz D. L., Davies M. R. D., Forth C. J. P., Hilditch M. A., Oldfield M. L. G. and Sheard A. G., "A Transient Flow Facility for the Study of the Thermofluid-Dynamics of a Full Stage Turbine Under Engine Representative Conditions," ASME Turbo Expo 88-GT-144, pp. 1-14, 1988.
- [5] Chana K., Cardwell D. and Jones T., "A Review of the Oxford Turbine Research Facility," ASME Turbo Expo 2013, GT2013-95687, 2013.
- [6] Chana K., Povey T., Paniagua G., Schultz A., Martelli F., Smith A. and Remi O., "Turbine Aero-Thermal External Flows II: A European 6th Framework Programme Addressing the High Pressure Turbine," Proceedings of the 8th European Conference on Turbomachinery, Graz, Austria, 2009.
- [7] Beard P. F., Povey T. and Chana K. S., "Turbine Efficiency Measurement System for the QinetiQ Turbine Test Facility," J. Turbomachinery, Vol. 132, pp. 1-13, 2010.
- [8] Chana K. S., Singh U. K. and Povey T., "Turbine Heat Transfer and Aerodynamic Measurements and Predictions for A 1.5 Stage Configuration," ASME Turbo Expo, GT-2004-53951, pp. 1-8, 2004.
- [9] Johnson A. B., Rigby M. J., Oldfield M. L. G., Ainsworth R. W. and Oliver M. J., "Surface Heat Transfer Fluctuations on a Turbine Rotor Blade Due to Upstream Shock Wave Passing," Journal of Turbomachinery, Vol. 111, pp. 105-115, 1989.
- [10] Ainsworth R. W., Allen J. L. and Dietz A. J., "Methods for Making Unsteady Aerodynamic Pressure Measurements in a Rotating Turbine Stage," AGARD CP-486, 1989.
- [11] Hilditch M. A., Fowler A., Jones T. V., Chana K. S., Oldfield M. L. G., Ainsworth R. W., Hogg S. I., Anderson S. J. and Smith G. C., "Installation Of A Turbine Stage In The Pyestock Isentropic Light Piston Facility," ASME Turbo Expo 94-GT-277, pp. 1-9, 1994.
- [12] Hilditch M. A., Smith G. C., Anderson J. S., Chana K. S., Jones T. V., Ainsworth R. W. and Oldfield M. L. G., "Unsteady Measurements in an Axial Flow Turbine," 85th Propulsion and Energetic Panel Symposium on Loss Mechanism and Unsteady Flows in Turbomachines, Derby, AGARD CP-571, pp. 333-340, 1996.

- [13] Johansson M., Martensson J., Abrahamsson H., Povey T. and Chana K., "Aerothermal Measurements and Predictions of an Intermediate Turbine Duct Turning Vane," ASME Turbo Expo GT2015-43449, 2015.
- [14] Goodisman M. I., Oldfield M. L. G., Kingcombe R. C., Jones T. V., Ainsworth R. W. and Brooks A. J., "An axial turbobrake," ASME Journal of Turbomachinery, Vol. 114, pp. 419-425, 1992.
- [15] Qureshi I., Beretta A. and Povey T., "Effect of Simulated Combustor Temperature Non-Uniformity on HP Vane and Endwall Heat Transfer: An Experimental and Computational Investigation," ASME Turbo Expo GT2010-22702, 2010.
- [16] Harasgama S. P., Burton C. D. and Chana K. S., "Measurements and computations of heat transfer and film cooling in turbines," ISABE Nottingham UK, 1991.
- [17] Chana K. S., "Heat transfer and aerodynamics of a 3D design nozzle guide vane tested in the Pyestock isentropic light piston facility," AGARD-CP-527, 1992.
- [18] Harvey N. W., "Heat transfer studies on an HP NGV in annular cascade in the Pyestock isentropic light piston facility," IMT Area 3 Turbine Project AER2-CT-92-0044, 1993.
- [19] Rose M. G., "MT1 turbine background information," IMT Area 3 Turbine Project AER2-CT-92-0044 report, 1993.
- [20] Beard P. F., Adams M. G., Nagawakar J. R., Stokes M. R., Wallin F., Cardwell D. N., Povey T. and Chana K., "The LEMCOTEC 1.5 Stage Film Cooled HP Turbine Design Integration and Testing in the Oxford Turbine Research Facility," Proceedings of 13th European Conference on Turbomachinery Fluid dynamics & Thermodynamics, ETC2019-216, Lausanne, Switzerland, 2019.
- [21] Beard P. F., Povey T. and Ireland P. T., "Mass Flow Rate Measurement in a Transonic Turbine Test Facility with Temperature Distortion and Swirl," Journal of Flow Measurement and Instrumentation, Vol. 19(5), pp. 315-324, 2008.
- [22] Chana K. S. and Hilditch M. A., "A summary datum un-cooled measurements of the MT1 single stage high-pressure turbine in the DRA Pyestock Isen-tropic Light Piston Facility," IMT Area 3 Turbine Project AER2-CT92-0044 report (also DRA/AS/PTD/TR95046/1), 1995.
- [23] Hilditch M. A., "Initial Analysis of Unsteady Measurements of MT1 Turbine," IMT Area 3 Turbine Project AER2-CT92-0044 report (also DRA/AS/PTD/CR96112/1), 1996.
- [24] Falsetti C., Beard P. F., Cardwell D. N. and Chana K. S., "A Review of High-Speed Rotating HP Turbine Heat Transfer and Cooling Studies Over the Last Decade in the Oxford Turbine Research Facility," ASME Turbo Expo GT2022-81945, 2022.
- [25] Chana K. S. and Haller B., "Novel Turbine Rotor Shroud Film Cooling Design and Validation, Part I," ASME Turbo Expo GT2009-60242, 2009.
- [26] Chana K. S. and Haller B., "Novel Turbine Rotor Shroud Film Cooling Design and Validation, Part II," ASME Turbo Expo GT2009-60246, 2009.
- [27] Povey T. and Qureshi I., "Developments in Hot-Streak Simulators for Turbine Testing," Journal of Turbomachinery, Vol.131(3), 2009.
- [28] Milli A. and Shahpar S., "PADRAM: Parametric Design and Rapid Meshing System for Complex Turbomechinery Configurations," ASME Turbo Expo, GT2012-69030, pp. 1-14, 2012.
- [29] Shahpar S. and Lapworth L., "PADRAM: Parametric Design and Rapid Meshing System for Turbomachinery Optimisation," ASME Turbo Expo, GT2003-38698, 2003.
- [30] Lapworth L. and Shahpar S., "Design Of Gas Turbine Engines Using CFD," Proceedings of European Congress on Computational Methods in Applied Sciences and Engineering, ECCOMAS 2004, pp. 1-21, 2004.
- [31] Lapworth L., "Hydra-CFD: A Framework for Collaborative CFD Development," International Conference on Scientific & Engineering Computation (IC-SEC), 2004.
- [32] Moinier P., Müller J.-D. and Giles M. B., "Edge-Based Multigrid and Preconditioning for Hybrid Grids," AIAA Journal, Vol. 40, No. 10, 2001.
- [33] Hills N. J., "Achieving High Parallel Performance for Unsteady Turbomachinery Code," The Aeronautical Journal, UK Applied Aerodynamics Consortium Special Edition, vol. 111., 2007.
- [34] Salvadori S., Adami P. and Martelli F., "On the Implementation of a Phase Lag Approach for Multi-Row Simulations," Proceedings of 10th International Symposium on Experimental Computational Aerothermodynamics of Internal Flows, Brussels, Belgium, 2011.
- [35] Salvadori S., Adami P., Martelli F. and Chana K., "Numerical Investigation of the Unsteady Flows in a Transonic Axial Flow Turbine With Temperature Distortions," Proceedings of the 8th European Conference on Turbomachinery, Graz, Austria, 2009.
- [36] Hirsch C., "Numerical Computation of Internal and External Flows," John Wiley and Sons, 1990.
- [37] Crumpton P. I. and Giles M. B., "OPLUS Fortran 77," <http://www.comlab.ox.ac.uk>, 2002.
- [38] Zamboni G. and Adami P., "On The Unsteady Interaction Between The Leakage And The Main Passage Flow In A High Pressure Turbine Rig: CFD URANS Investigations and Comparison with the Rig Test Data," ASME Turbo Expo GT2016-56041, pp. 1-13, 2016.